

Soil sampling and lab extraction guidelines for QBS-ar analysis

- **Sampling period:** Winter and summer should be avoided since cold and hot temperatures reduce the activity/presence of the soil fauna (Joseph *et al.*, 2014). In temperate climates, **early springtime** or early autumn are generally the most suitable period for sampling, which preferably should be repeated in the same season and environmental conditions. In the Excalibur project baseline, sampling was planned just **before plot treatments**, during early springtime 2021, in almost all cases. A check should be done to assess if other animals and plants are active during the sampling time. Similarly, **extreme** circadian conditions, such as night and Astronomical Noon, or special meteorological conditions, such as heavy rain should be excluded.
- **Area identification:** To increase the area representativeness, the **3 replicates** should be collected at the same time generally at least **10-15 m apart**, to represent the soil conditions of the whole trial area. Soil conditions should be checked by topsoil analyses and/or **proximal sensors**, eventually corroborated by pedological profile analysis. The area should be **homogeneous** for slope and plant vegetation (Parisi *et al.*, 2005). **Limiting factors** should be avoided, i.e. overabundance of animals (e.g., *Formicidae*), local decomposition of the organic matter (e.g., animal remains), short time proximity of deep tillage, extreme soil compaction (D'Avino, 2002). The days since the last farming practices should be noted down, especially if the gap from the last tillage is less than 10 days. The 3 replicates should be representative of the whole study area. For instance, in orchard, during EXCALIBUR baseline sampling, we used proximal sensing, and we sample at least 1 replicate in non-compacted interrow and 1 along the row almost 20 cm from the stem or trunk. The exact point of all replicates on the map must be marked.
- **Soil conditions:** Soil must **not be dry but even not too wet**, i.e., indicatively, it does not have to change appreciably its color by adding water, and it does not have to drip down if squeezed between the index and the thumb, respectively. No sampling after a big downpour should be considered viable (Parisi, 2001), especially if there are puddles in the trial field. On the other hand, the best period for sampling soil is away from the dry period, because this condition causes vertical migration, immobilization, and aestivation of soil microarthropods (Menta *et al.*, 2017). The limiting soil **temperature (measured at 5 cm depth) should be preferably between 8°C and 20°C**.
- **Sampling:** A **spade and/or a flat trowel**, scissors, plastic bags, thermometer, and labeling equipment are needed (D'Avino *ib.*; Joseph *et al. ib.*); a ruler or better three 10x10 plastic or metal tiles and hammer could help. In each site for each unit, **3 soil cubes of 10x10x10 cm**, are collected (about 1 liter of soil, stones excluded). Only the soil is taken, the upper litter layer can be gently removed before sampling, if present (Parisi *ib.*; Joseph *et al. ib.*), and **plants are cut at the collars by scissors**. During sampling, try to minimize vibrations and be relatively quick to avoid microarthropods escape. The soil must be preserved in sealed plastic bags (retaining some extra air volume), preserved and transported to avoid any shock, such as bumps, **exposition to the direct sun** (possibly bring them in polystyrene or cool box, with some thermal packs), and then set up for **extraction as soon as possible, at maximum within 24-48 hours. Weight the sample after (and optionally before) the extraction**.
- **Arthropods' extraction (Berlese-Tüllgren funnel** or by MacFadyen and Kempson extractors): spotlight about 40-60W depending on lamp type, large funnel, mesh (size 2mm), and collecting vessel with preservative liquid (e.g. 3 parts 70-75° ethanol and 1-part glycerol) are needed. Place the clod on the mesh and gently break it to distribute it roughly on the mesh. Use a container (e.g., a beaker or Petri dish) under the funnel to gather any fallen dirt or animals and replace it on the top. The vessel with preservative liquid shall be placed down the mesh only once the soil is firmly stabilized in, to avoid the eventual fall of soil grains in the fixer liquid during its accommodation. The extraction system should be kept free from vibrations and other disturbances. (Parisi *et al. ib.*). The heat source, placed 15-30 cm above the soil sample, dries the soil on the sieve gradually, driving the microarthropods into the deeper soil layer, until they fall into the container under the funnel. **The temperature on the mesh shall be 25±5°C**. The extraction time is in relation to the heat source power and to the soil water content, **never less than 5 days** (Menta *et al.*, 2018), generally 7-15 in relation to the soil water content. Be careful that **preservative liquid does not completely evaporate**, because in this case the sample gets lost. If necessary, add more alcohol, without touching the mesh. In the end, clean thoroughly the funnels without surfactant detergents, brush it carefully or, alternatively, flush them several times with water and dry them preferably with a non-synthetic cloth.

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Cited Reference

D'Avino L. (2002) -Esposizione del metodo di Vittorio Parisi per la valutazione della Qualità Biologica del Suolo (QBS) e proposta di standardizzazione delle procedure [Exposition of Vittorio Parisi's method for the assessment of the Biological Soil Quality (QBS) and proposal for standardized protocol, in Italian]. Museo di Storia Naturale, Dipartimento di Biologia Evolutiva e Funzionale, Università degli Studi di Parma. Parma. Available free at QBS SISS working group database <https://scienzadelsuolo.org/QBS-ar.php> (accessed 30/08/2022)

Joseph, A., Groner, E., Menta, C. (2014). Soil macrofaunal diversity in Firbank, L., Bertora, C., Blankman, D., Delle Vedove, G., Frenzel, M., Grignani, C., Groner, E., Joseph A., Kertész, M., Kunin, B., Matteucci, G., Menta, C. Müller, C., Stadler, J., Handbook for Standardised Ecosystem Protocols available at <http://www.expeeronline.eu/expeer-protocols.html> (accessed 30/08/2022)

Menta C., Conti F.D., Pinto S., Bodini A. (2018). Soil Biological Quality index (QBS-ar): 15 years of application at global scale. Ecological Indicators, 85: 773-780.

Parisi V., Menta C., Gardi C., Jacomini C., Mozzanica E. (2005). Microarthropod Communities as a Tool to Assess Soil Quality and Biodiversity: a new Approach in Italy. Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment 105: 323-333. 17.